

A SIMPLE SINUSOIDAL QUADRATURE OSCILLATOR USING A SINGLE ACTIVE ELEMENT

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Abstract

This study describes a simple design for a single active element sinusoidal oscillator with a quadrature signal. A current conveyor transconductance amplifier (CCTA), a single resistor, and two grounded capacitors are used in the first circuit. The second circuit is improved by using a current-controlled current conveyor transconductance amplifier (CCCCTA) and two grounded capacitors without a passive resistor, which means the grounded capacitor is suitably implemented for the IC fabrication. The oscillation condition and frequency of both circuits can be controlled using the same method that concurrently adjusts the DC bias current and the resistance as well as the oscillation frequency can be independently adjusted by capacitances. The CCTA is achieved by cascading the integrated circuits (IC) AD844 and LM13700, made by Analog Devices Corporation and Texas Instruments, respectively, which are available for commercial purchase. The sinusoidal quadrature signals in the time-domain and frequency-domain can be shown with computer simulations and the results of experiments. The Monte Carlo Analysis is also utilized to examine the oscillation frequency with the influence of passive element tolerance errors. The predicted oscillation frequency has a standard variation of about 20.04 kHz, with a maximum frequency of approximately 346.89 kHz and a minimum frequency of approximately 259.09 kHz. In addition, the mean and median frequencies are 296.10 and 293.98 kHz, respectively. The results of this study indicate that computer simulation and experiment are similar to a theoretical analysis, making them suitable for use in the teaching of electrical and electronic engineering.

Keywords: single active element, sinusoidal quadrature oscillator, CCTA, CCCCTA, grounded capacitor, frequency of oscillation, condition of oscillation.

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1. Introduction

The sinusoidal quadrature oscillator consists of two sinusoidal signals with a 90-degree phase difference. It is useful widely in communication, measurement, and instrumentation systems. Moreover, the sinusoidal quadrature oscillator is used as examples [1–3] in the modulation and demodulation of quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM). In electrical and electronics engineering labs, sinusoidal signals have also been widely employed for teaching and learning [4, 5]. The circuit for a sinusoidal oscillator that uses an active building block (ABB) is very interesting because it can easily be applied and used in various works [1–4]. Specially, the laboratory equipment can be implemented and tested to present the performance of a circuit as in [1, 4, 5].

Active building blocks are extensively employed in analog signal processing nowadays, and the current conveyor transconductance amplifier (CCTA) [6] is one of them. The CCTA is used in analog signal processing, such as in sinusoidal oscillators [7–11], and has been the subject of a number of papers and studies. Consequently, the current-controlled current conveyor transconductance amplifier (CCCCTA) [12] has been upgraded from a CCTA to a CCCCTA by using a current-controlled function to operate the internal resistance. It is widely applicable to design of sinusoidal

oscillators, for example in voltage-mode [13–17] and current-mode [18–21]. The following example is advantageous for the sinusoidal oscillator designs that employ CCTA and CCCCTA. The oscillators described in references [22–24] can be adjusted electronically to tune the oscillation frequency and condition, which are conveniently controlled for tuning by microcontrollers and microprocessors. The proposed circuits in [8, 25–27] use only grounded capacitors, which are also used for making up ICs. The sinusoidal oscillators presented in [25–28] use a single active element that is readily implemented and tested. Furthermore, the output sinusoidal signals in [11, 18, 21] have been generated simultaneously in voltage-mode and current-mode.

Nevertheless, several studies of circuits have identified the following flaws:

- their sinusoidal signals are neither quadrature signals nor 90-degree phase differences [12, 14–15, 26, 28], which is inconvenient in communication systems;
- the transconductance gain of the CCTA or CCCCTA must be at least two [15, 21, 25] which is mistaken for the standard internal structure;
- they require two z -terminals [7, 11, 15, 16, 18, 21–26, 28] and more than two o -terminals of CCTA or CCCCTA [7, 16, 21, 25, 28], whose internal structure is large and complicated to implement;
- at least two CCTAs or CCCCTAs [7, 8, 10, 17–20, 22–24] with increased power constraints are required;
- CCTAs or CCCCTAs must be modified through internal construction [9, 16], resulting in a larger structure that is hard to implement and test;
- they have not been implemented as the result of the experiments [7, 8, 10–16, 19, 21–28].

The purpose of this study is to describe a sinusoidal quadrature oscillator based on a single active element. For the first sinusoidal oscillator, a single CCTA, a single resistor, and two grounded capacitors are utilized. Similarly, the second circuit is made with a single CCCCTA, and capacitors that are connected to the ground, but without any external resistor. The condition of oscillation is controlled by a DC bias current. The efficiency of the circuit is shown through computer simulations and experiments according to the theory.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. The description of CCTA and CCCCTA

The CCTA is a current conveyor transconductance amplifier that was researched and published in 2005 [6]. The electrical symbol, and equivalent circuit are shown in **Fig. 1, a, b**. The input voltage at the y -terminal has a high impedance, whereas the voltage at the x -terminal is equivalent to that at the y -terminal and has a low impedance. The z -terminal is an output port with a current equal to that of the x -terminal and has a high impedance. Additionally, the output current at the o -terminal is dependent on V_z and transconductance gain. The electrical features of the CCTA are characterized by the following matrix function:

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_y \\ V_x \\ I_z \\ I_o \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \pm g_m & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_x \\ V_y \\ V_z \\ V_o \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where g_m is the transconductance gain, which is controlled proportionally by the DC bias current as:

$$g_m = I_B / 2V_T. \quad (2)$$

In practice, CCTA can be achieved via cascading a current conveyor version II (CCII) at the front-end and an operational transconductance amplifier (OTA) at the rear-end, both of which are commercially available [11].

The reference [12] was updated from CCTA to CCCCTA (current-controlled current conveyor transconductance amplifier) in 2008, as shown by the electrical symbol and equivalent circuit in **Fig. 2, a, b**, respectively. The x -terminal is designed with an internal resistance of CCCCTA that is called R_x .

Fig. 1. Current conveyor transconductance amplifier: *a* – Electrical symbol; *b* – Equivalent circuit

Fig. 2. Current-controlled current conveyor transconductance amplifier:
a – Electrical symbol; *b* – Equivalent circuit

The electrical characteristics are modified to:

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_y \\ V_x \\ I_z \\ I_o \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ R_x & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \pm g_m & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_x \\ V_y \\ V_z \\ V_o \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

and R_x is electronically adjusted by the DC bias current as shown in this equation:

$$R_x = V_T / 2I_A. \quad (4)$$

2. 2. Proposed sinusoidal quadrature oscillators

The schematic designs of the two proposed sinusoidal quadrature oscillators are shown in Fig. 3, *a*, *b*. The first proposed circuit is shown in Fig. 3, *a* which is a simple and compact design by a single CCTA, a single resistor, and two grounded capacitors. The grounded capacitor is a requirement for IC manufacture, and its capacity at node or port can be eliminated [1]. Furthermore, both sinusoidal signals are voltage-mode, with V_{O1} and V_{O2} being phase-shifted by 90 degrees. Using the electrical properties of CCTA in equation (1), the characteristic equation for Fig. 3, *a* is presented:

$$s^2 + s \frac{2}{C_1 R_x} \left(\frac{g_m R_x}{2} - 1 \right) + \frac{2g_m}{C_1 C_2 R_x} = 0. \quad (5)$$

The circuit will be able to generate sinusoidal signals if the condition of oscillation (*CO*) is set up as:

$$\frac{g_m R_x}{2} \approx 1. \quad (6)$$

The frequency of oscillation (*FO*) of the proposed sinusoidal oscillator can be expressed as:

$$\omega_{osc} = \sqrt{\frac{2g_m}{C_1 C_2 R_x}}. \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3. Proposed circuits: *a* – Current conveyor transconductance amplifier;
b – Current-controlled current conveyor transconductance amplifier

From equations (6), (7), it is possible to adjust the CO and FO by maintaining the ratio of g_m and R_x , which is $g_m = 2/R_x$. However, the FO can be controlled separately using grounded capacitors.

Sinusoidal signals are generated by the proposed circuit with V_{O1} and V_{O2} , whose ratio can be expressed as:

$$\frac{V_{O1}(s)}{V_{O2}(s)} = -\frac{g_m}{sC_1}. \quad (8)$$

It is confirmed that the sinusoidal signals of V_{O1} and V_{O2} are phase-shifted by 90 degrees and that the signal V_{O1} is the leading phase of the signal V_{O2} .

Nevertheless, when CO is set and FO is substituted into equation (8), the magnitude ratios of V_{O1} and V_{O2} are calculated as shown in equation (9), which is equivalent to:

$$\left| \frac{V_{O1}}{V_{O2}} \right|_{\omega=\omega_{osc}} = 1. \quad (9)$$

Fig. 3, b depicts the design of the second proposed sinusoidal quadrature oscillator, which is small and compact because it consists of a single CCCCTA, and two grounded capacitors without a passive resistor. However, without a passive resistor, the power consumption may be reduced, and the circuit uses only a grounded capacitor, which is a prerequisite for the development of IC manufacture. The sinusoidal oscillator produces sinusoidal signals with a 90-degree phase shift as the equivalent of the circuit in **Fig. 3, a**. Furthermore, the features of the circuit in **Fig. 3, b** are exactly the same as those in **Fig. 3, a**, including the characteristic equations, CO , and FO , which are represented by equations (5)–(7), respectively.

Substituting the g_m from equation (2) and the R_x from equation (4) into equation (6) results in the following expression for the modification of CO , let's obtain:

$$\frac{I_B}{4I_A} \approx 1. \quad (10)$$

Again, the FO can be modified by replacing g_m in equation (2) and R_x in equation (4) into equation (7). These can be represented as:

$$\omega_{osc} = \sqrt{\frac{2I_A I_B}{C_1 C_2 V_T^2}}. \quad (11)$$

It has been found that the CO and FO can be electronically controlled using DC bias currents, which can be implemented using a microcontroller or microprocessor. The CO and FO in equations (10) and (11) are both relative so that the DC bias currents of I_A and I_B are adjusted by maintaining the same ratio. Using a current mirror circuit, it is possible to solve the ratio of these currents in practice.

The phase relationship of sinusoidal signals V_{O1} and V_{O2} and their ratio in the proposed circuit of **Fig. 3, b** are exactly the same as in equations (8), (9) for the first circuit, respectively.

Hence, it is interested that the proposed circuits are simple and smart due to their design utilizing a single active element and grounded capacitors. The CCTA and CCCCTA are constructed using just a single z-terminal and a single transconductance gain, with no modifications to the internal structure necessary. In addition, the oscillation condition and the oscillation frequency can be configured or adjusted by using DC bias currents, as well as the oscillation frequency can be freely altered using external grounded capacitors, as analyzed in equations (6) and (7), respectively. The ability to generate sinusoidal signals with a 90-degree phase shift and its ratio are declared in equation (8) and (9), respectively.

2. 3. The non-ideal analysis

In the practical application of CCTA and CCCCTA, the tracking error of voltage and current, as well as the parasitic elements, are supplied. Errors and the parasitic elements have an effect on the performance of the proposed circuits, making an investigation of their influence essential.

Ideally, these tracking errors must be equal to 1. However, the voltage and current tracking errors of CCTAs and CCCCTAs are caused by their flawed internal structures. When γ is a voltage tracking error from y -terminal to x -terminal, α is a current tracking error from x -terminal to z -terminal and β represents the voltage tracking error from z -terminal to o-terminal, thus the matrix equation may represent these tracking errors as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_y \\ V_x \\ I_z \\ I_o \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \pm\beta g_m & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_x \\ V_y \\ V_z \\ V_o \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

and

$$\begin{bmatrix} I_y \\ V_x \\ I_z \\ I_o \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ R_x & \gamma & 0 & 0 \\ \alpha & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \pm\beta g_m & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_x \\ V_y \\ V_z \\ V_o \end{bmatrix}, \quad (13)$$

where the electrical characteristics of CCTAs and CCCCTAs are described by equations (12) and (13), respectively.

The parasitic elements appearing on the high impedance terminal, such as C_y and R_y , are connected to ground via the y -terminal. C_z and R_z are grounded via the z -terminal, whereas C_o and R_o are also grounded via the o-terminal. R_{xi} is the internal resistance at the x -terminal. The parasitic elements included in the proposed circuits are represented in **Fig. 4**. Where $R_x > R_{xi}$, the characteristic equations of the proposed circuits in **Fig. 4, a, b** are re-analyzed using the electrical characteristics in equations (12) and (13), as well as parasitic elements, which are rewritten as:

$$s^2 + s \frac{2}{Y_1 R_x} \left(\frac{\beta g_m R_x}{2} - 1 \right) + \frac{2\beta g_m}{Y_1 Y_2 R_x} = 0, \quad (14)$$

where $G_y = 1/R_y$, $G_z = 1/R_z$, $G_o = 1/R_o$, $G_{o-} = 1/R_{o-}$, $Y_1 = C_1 + C_z + C_o + G_z + G_o$ and $Y_2 = C_2 + C_y + C_{o-} + G_y + G_{o-}$. Thus, the FO is re-analyzed and written as:

$$\omega_{osc} = \sqrt{\frac{2\beta g_m}{Y_1 Y_2 R_x}}. \quad (15)$$

Likewise, the phase relation in equation (8) and the amplitude ratio in equation (9) are also affected by tracking errors and parasitic elements. But either the DC bias current or the resistance can be changed to reduce this effect by a large amount.

Fig. 4. The proposed circuits showing parasitic elements:
a – current conveyor transconductance amplifier; *b* – current-controlled current conveyor transconductance amplifier

3. Results and discussion

A computer simulation of the first proposed sinusoidal quadrature oscillator, as seen in **Fig. 3**, *a* was performed to assess the performance and theoretical validity of the circuit by using the PSPICE program. A current conveyor version II and an operational transconductance amplifier are employed in the construction of a CCTA by cascading the commercially available ICs AD844 [29] from Analog Device and LM13700 [30] from Texas Instruments, respectively, as shown in **Fig. 5**. The AD844 and LM13700 macro-models are used. The power supply is configured to ± 5 V, and the passive capacitors C_1 and C_2 have standard values of 1 nF. The *CO* and *FO* are designed with a passive resistor of value $R_x = 1$ k Ω , and the DC bias is set to 125 μ A. The *FO* for this setup can be determined by using equation (7) at 336.27 kHz.

Fig. 5. The construction of a current conveyor transconductance amplifier

The first result of the simulation is shown in **Fig. 6**, which is the output of the sinusoidal quadrature signals in their transient state at a timing between 0 and 400 μ s. **Fig. 7** simulates the

steady state of signals, which is between 384 μs and 400 μs . The phase of the sinusoidal signal of V_{O1} is about 90 degrees ahead of the phase of the sinusoidal signal of V_{O2} and the amplitude of signals is identical, according to the theory in equations (8) and (9), respectively.

Fig. 6. Transient stage of sinusoidal quadrature signals

Fig. 7. Steady stage of sinusoidal quadrature signals

Fig. 8 shows the output spectrum of sinusoidal signals produced by a 300 kHz frequency oscillation. The inaccuracy of FO is around 10.78 % and is caused by internal tracking errors and parasitic elements, as demonstrated in the topic of non-ideal analysis. The total harmonic distortion (THD) values for V_{O1} and V_{O2} are 3.84 % and 2.85 %, respectively.

Additionally, the tolerance errors of the passive elements have impacted the functioning of the circuits once again. The Monte Carlo Analysis must be used to investigate these mistakes so that the frequency of the sinusoidal signal can be predicted. The Monte Carlo Analysis was configured to a Gaussian distribution for 100 samples, and the resistor and capacitor tolerance errors were defined as 1 % and 10 %, respectively.

The simulation results of the Monte Carlo Analysis are presented in **Table 1** with their statistical component values. The mean and median frequencies of FO are 296.10 and 293.98 kHz, respectively. The FO has a minimum frequency of 254.09 kHz and a maximum frequency of 346.89 kHz. Furthermore, **Fig. 9** shows the spread spectrums, and **Fig. 10** plots the frequency histogram.

Fig. 8. Spectrums of sinusoidal quadrature signals

Fig. 9. Spread spectrums of sinusoidal quadrature signals

Fig. 10. Frequency histograms

Table 1
The statistical outputs

The values of statistical components					
Total samples	Mean (kHz)	Median (kHz)	Standard deviation (kHz)	Maximum (kHz)	Minimum (kHz)
100	296.10	293.98	20.04	346.89	254.09

The performance of the proposed sinusoidal quadrature oscillator shown in **Fig. 3, a** was investigated by experimental means. The power supply was set with a voltage supply of ± 5 V by a Siglent SPD3303C. The passive elements were specified as $C_1 = C_2 = 1$ nF and $R_x = 1$ k Ω . The circuit produced sinusoidal signals when the oscillation condition was set at a DC bias current, $I_B = 125$ μ A, which corresponds to the circumstances in the equation (6). A Keysight 34461A was used to test this bias current. An oscilloscope from Keysight DSOX3024T was used to measure and show the results of the experiment with sinusoidal waveforms and parameters.

Fig. 11 illustrates the experimental outcomes of the quadrature sinusoidal waveforms. The FO was 325.90 kHz, which was around 3.08 % incorrect, which is in accordance with the Monte Carlo Analysis prediction. The phase difference between V_{O1} and V_{O2} was 90.158 degrees and their amplitudes were comparable in size, as predicted by theoretical studies in equations (8) and (9), respectively. As described in the previous section, frequency, phase, and amplitude errors can be caused by the tolerance errors of passive elements, the tracking errors of voltage and current, and the parasitic elements of the CCTA.

Fig. 11. Experimental results of quadrature sinusoidal waveforms

The spectrums of the sinusoidal signals are displayed in **Fig. 12, a, b**, which represent the sinusoidal signals V_{O1} and V_{O2} , respectively. The total harmonic distortion (THD) of the sinusoidal output V_{O1} is approximately 2.60 %, and the fundamental frequency amplitude is greater than that of the other harmonics, at approximately 30.80 dB while the THD of the sinusoidal output V_{O2} is around 2.40 %, and the magnitude of the fundamental frequency is greater than that of the other harmonics, at approximately 32.40 dB.

It can be seen that the simulation and experiment are easily implemented using the commercially available ICs. The simulation of the phase difference between the outcomes of sinusoidal signals is about 90 degrees, and the ratio of amplitude is nearly size. The Monte Carlo method is used to forecast, based on the influence of tolerance errors, that the mean frequency is approximately 296.10 kHz. The experiment is enjoyable since the amplitude of the sinusoidal waveforms differs slightly and the phase is close to 90 degrees. In addition, the signal spectrums revealed that the amplitude of the fundamental frequency is roughly 30 dB greater than that of other frequencies. The results are interested to apply for circuits in the communication system and laboratory education.

Although the proposed quadrature oscillator circuits have many useful applications, they have some restrictions. For example, the demand for a voltage buffer connected the output signals to the next circuit or stage. They have been required the frequency adjustment to be maintained within a specific ratio of R_1 and g_m . The LM13700 has a DC bias current of less than 2 mA, which limits its oscillation frequency. Also, both the bandwidths of the LM13700 and the AD844 have some limits on the oscillation frequency.

Fig. 12. The spectra of the sinusoidal outputs: *a* – V_{O1} ; *b* – V_{O2}

4. Conclusions

Two sinusoidal quadrature oscillators were designed and experimented.

The first circuit consisted of a single CCTA, a single resistor, and two grounded capacitors, making its construction simple. The second minimally compact circuit consisted of a single CCCCTA and two grounded capacitors. The grounded capacitor could be developed further in IC manufacturing. The sinusoidal quadrature signals have a phase difference of 90 degrees and an equal amplitude.

The proposed circuit can be made with AD844 at the front end and LM13700 at the back end, which are commercially available ICs that can be cascaded together. A computer simulation using the PSPICE program was checked and confirmed, and the results accord with those of the theoretical studies. The outcomes of the experiment were congruent with the theoretical investigations. Nevertheless, the simulation and experiment outcomes include mistakes, as predicted by the Monte Carlo Analysis.

It can therefore be concluded that the proposed circuits are suitable for design a worksheet that can be used in electronic laboratory.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in relation to this research, whether financial, personal, authorship or otherwise, that could affect the research and its results presented in this paper.

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Data availability

Manuscript has no associated data.

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References

- [1] Jaikla, W., Adhan, S., Suwanjan, P., Kumngern, M. (2020). Current/Voltage Controlled Quadrature Sinusoidal Oscillators for Phase Sensitive Detection Using Commercially Available IC. *Sensors*, 20 (5), 1319. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20051319>
- [2] Arora, T. S., Singh, A. K. (2022). A new voltage mode sinusoidal quadrature oscillator employing second generation voltage conveyor. *AEU – International Journal of Electronics and Communications*, 154, 154304. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aeu.2022.154304>
- [3] Prommee, P. (2017). Integrable CMOS-Based Current-Mode Sinusoidal Frequency and Peak Detector. *Circuits, Systems, and Signal Processing*, 36 (12), 4937–4962. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00034-017-0604-8>
- [4] Kwawsibsam, A., Duangmalai, D., Yeeyoun, S., Jaikla, W. (2022). Electronically and Independently Controllable Quadrature Sinusoidal Oscillator with Low Output Impedances. *Advances in Electrical and Electronic Engineering*, 20 (3), 304–313. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15598/aeue.v20i3.4513>
- [5] Pawasarn, S., Charoenmee, A., Janda, T., Fungdeth, S., Patimaprakorn, K., Jantakun, A. (2021). Implementation of Low-output-impedance sinusoidal oscillator and its modification for use in filters. *Przegląd Elektrotechniczny*, 1 (8), 98–105. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15199/48.2021.08.17>
- [6] Prokop, R., Musil, V. (2005). New modern circuit block CCCTA and some its application, *ELECTRONICS' 2005*. Sozopol, 36–42. Available at: https://ecad.tu-sofia.bg/et/2005/pdf/Paper151-V_Musil2.pdf
- [7] Summart, S., Saetiauw, C., Thongsopa, C., Jaikla, W. (2013). CCTA Based Current-mode first order filter and its application in quadrature oscillator. *Przegląd Elektrotechniczny*, 89, 104–108. Available at: <http://pe.org.pl/articles/2013/6/17.pdf>
- [8] Thosdeekoraphat, T., Summart, S., Saetiauw, C., Santalunai, S., Thongsopa, C. (2013). CCTAs based Current-mode Quadrature Oscillator with High Output Impedances. *International Journal of Electronics and Electrical Engineering*, 1 (1), 52–56. doi: <https://doi.org/10.12720/ijeee.1.1.52-56>
- [9] Sotner, R., Jeraber, J., Prokop, R., Vrba, K. (2011). Current gain controlled CCTA and its application in quadrature oscillator and direct frequency modulator. *Radioengineering*, 20 (1), 317–326. Available at: https://www.radioeng.cz/fulltexts/2011/11_01_317_326.pdf
- [10] Sotner, R., Slezak, J., Dostal, T. (2010). Tunable oscillator using two CCTA-s and only grounded passive elements. *9th International Conference on Environment and Electrical Engineering*, 447–450, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEEIC.2010.5489914>
- [11] Lahiri, A. (2009). Explicit-current-output quadrature oscillator using second-generation current conveyor transconductance amplifier. *Radioengineering*, 18 (4), 522–526. Available at: https://www.radioeng.cz/fulltexts/2009/09_04_522_526.pdf
- [12] Siripruchyanun, M., Jaikla, W. (2008). Current controlled current conveyor transconductance amplifier (CCCCTA): a building block for analog signal processing. *Electrical Engineering*, 90 (6), 443–453. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00202-007-0095-x>
- [13] Duanmalai, D., Jaikla, W. (2011). Realization of current-mode quadrature oscillator based on third order technique. *ACEEE Int. J. on Electrical and Power Engineering*, 2 (3), 46–49.
- [14] Jantakun, A., Sa-ngiamvibool, W. (2013). Current-mode sinusoidal oscillator using current controlled current conveyor transconductance amplifier. *Rev. Roum. Sci. Techn.-Électrotechn. et Énerg.*, 58 (4), 415–423. Available at: <http://revue.elth.pub.ro/upload/78611909AJantakun42013pp415-423.pdf>
- [15] Bumrongchok, T., Jaikla, W., Siripruchyanun, M. (2009). An electronic controllable, simple current-mode oscillator using single MO-CCCCTA and grounded capacitors. *The 1st International Conference on Technical Education (ICTE2009)*. Bangkok. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228901507_An_electronic_controllable_simple_current-mode_oscillator_using_single_MO-CCCCTA_and_grounded_capacitors
- [16] Kumngern, M., Torteanchai, U. (2012). Current-controlled quadrature oscillator using a new single ZC-CG-CCCCTA. *Second International Conference on Digital Information and Communication Technology and its Applications (DICTAP)*, 267–270. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/DICTAP.2012.6215354>

- [17] Jantakun, A. (2015) Current-mode quadrature oscillator using CCCCTAs with non-interactive current control for CO, FO and amplitude. *Journal of Microelectronics, Electronic Components and Materials*, 45 (1), 47–56. Available at: [http://www.midem-drustvo.si/Journal%20papers/MIDEM_45\(2015\)1p47.pdf](http://www.midem-drustvo.si/Journal%20papers/MIDEM_45(2015)1p47.pdf)
- [18] Chen, H.-P., Hwang, Y.-S., Ku, Y.-T. (2017). Voltage-Mode and Current-Mode Resistorless Third-Order Quadrature Oscillator. *Applied Sciences*, 7 (2), 179. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app7020179>
- [19] Singh, S. V., Gupta, G., Chhabra, R., Nagpal, K., Devansh (2010). Electronically tunable voltage-mode biquad filter/oscillator based on CCCCTAs. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security*. Available at: <https://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/1306/1306.5412.pdf>
- [20] Sa-Ngiamvibool, W., Jantakun, A. (2014). Quadrature oscillator using CCCCTAs and grounded capacitors with amplitude controllability. *International Journal of Electronics*, 101 (12), 1737–1758. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207217.2014.896038>
- [21] Chen, H.-P., Wang, S.-F., Ku, Y.-T. (2015). CCCCTA-based resistorless voltage and current mode quadrature oscillator. *IEICE Electronics Express*, 12 (13). <https://doi.org/10.1587/elex.12.20150449>
- [22] Tanaphatsiri, C., Jaikla, W. (2011). Electronically Tunable Four Phase Quadrature Oscillator Employing Current-Controlled Current Conveyor Transconductance Amplifiers. 2011 Sixth IEEE International Symposium on Electronic Design, Test and Application, 89–92. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/delta.2011.25>
- [23] Pitaksuttayaprot, L., Jaikla, W. (2013). Implementation of second order current-mode quadrature sinusoidal oscillator with current controllability. *World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology International Journal of Electronics and Communication Engineering*, 7 (3), 304–306. Available at: <https://publications.waset.org/4074/pdf>
- [24] Jantakun, A. (2017). The configuration of current-mode single-input multi-output, multi-input single-output biquad filter and quadrature oscillator based-on BiCMOS CCCTAs. *Przegląd Elektrotechniczny*, 1 (7), 104–109. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15199/48.2017.07.23>
- [25] Thosdeekoraphat, T., Summart, S., Thongsopa, C. (2013). Current-mode sinusoidal quadrature oscillator using single dual-output current controlled current conveyor transconductance amplifier (DO-CCCCTA). *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 7 (8), 230–236. Available at: <http://www.ajbasweb.com/old/ajbas/2013/June/230-236.pdf>
- [26] Tangsrirat, W., Channumsin, O., Pukkalanun, T. (2015). Single-current-controlled sinusoidal oscillator with current and voltage outputs using current-controlled conveyor transconductance amplifier and grounded passive elements. *Rev. Roum. Sci. Techn.-Électrotechn. et Énerg.*, 60 (2), 175–184. Available at: http://revue.elth.pub.ro/upload/12294607WTangsrirat_2_2015_pp175-184.pdf
- [27] Tangsrirat, W. (2016). Dual-mode sinusoidal quadrature oscillator with single CCCTA and grounded capacitors. *Journal of Microelectronics, Electronic Components and Materials*, 46 (3), 130–135. Available at: [http://www.midem-drustvo.si/Journal%20papers/MIDEM_46\(2016\)3p130.pdf](http://www.midem-drustvo.si/Journal%20papers/MIDEM_46(2016)3p130.pdf)
- [28] Phanikhom, S., Jantakun, A. (2014) Simple current-mode sinusoidal oscillator using single CCCCTA and grounded capacitors. The 4th Joint International Conference on Information and Communication Technology, Electronic and Electrical Engineering (JICTEE). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/JICTEE.2014.6804123>
- [29] Wideband, Fast Settling Op Amp AD840. Analog Devices. Available at: <https://www.analog.com/media/en/technical-documentation/obsolete-data-sheets/2090974AD840.pdf>
- [30] LM13700 Dual Operational Transconductance Amplifiers with Linearizing Diodes and Buffers. Texas Instruments. Available at: <https://www.ti.com/lit/ds/symlink/lm13700.pdf>

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